

Molecular Topology and Curve-Linear Regression Modeling of Amino Acid Structures

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Abstract

Amino acids, the fundamental building blocks of proteins, play a pivotal role in various biological processes, including protein synthesis, metabolic pathways, neurotransmitter activity, and antibiotic production. In this study, a quantitative structure-property relationship (QSPR) analysis is conducted to investigate the correlation between a set of 10 degree-based molecular descriptors and key physicochemical properties like heat capacity (C_v), entropy (S), and thermal energy (E_{th}) of 19 naturally occurring amino acids. Multiple regression models, including linear, logarithmic, quadratic, and cubic are employed to evaluate the predictive capabilities of the selected descriptors. The findings demonstrate that the degree-based molecular descriptors exhibit strong predictive potential for the studied physicochemical properties, highlighting their relevance in understanding amino acid behavior and their broader implications in molecular design and biophysical studies.

Keywords: Amino acids, molecular descriptors, physicochemical properties, regression models.

1 Introduction

Let $G = (V, E)$ be a graph with $|V| = n$ and $|E| = m$. The open neighbourhood of a vertex $v \in V$ is $N(v) = \{u/uv \in E\}$. The degree of a vertex v is $d_v = |N(v)|$. Molecular graphs provide a mathematical abstraction of molecular structures, where atoms are represented as vertices and chemical bonds as edges. This representation simplifies complex molecular structures, enabling their study using graph-theoretic tools. Constructing a molecular graph from a molecular structure involves mapping each atom to a vertex and each bond to an edge. The resulting graph preserves the connectivity of the molecular structure, capturing its topology and enabling quantitative analyses. In some cases, labels or weights may be added to the vertices and edges to distinguish between different types of atoms or bonds, reflecting their chemical properties.

Chemical graph theory is a branch of mathematical chemistry that focuses on the application of graph theory to study molecular structures and properties. By interpreting molecules as graphs, this field bridges mathematics and chemistry, providing a robust framework to analyze and predict molecular behavior. One of the central contributions of chemical graph theory is the development of molecular descriptors derived from the structural features of molecular graphs. These descriptors have been widely used in Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationships (QSAR) and Quantitative Structure-Property Relationships (QSPR). Chemical graph theory enables the correlation of molecular descriptors with various physical, chemical, and biological properties, aiding in the prediction of reactivity, stability, and other characteristics without extensive experimental effort. Molecular descriptors such as the Zagreb indices, Wiener index, and Randić index capture essential graph properties and have found applications in modeling the thermodynamic and electronic properties of molecules. This field has also extended beyond traditional organic molecules to study biomolecules, nanostructures, and materials, demonstrating its versatility. By combining graph theory with chemistry, chemical graph theory offers powerful tools to uncover structure-property relationships, advancing both

theoretical understanding and practical applications in molecular science.

Numerous studies have been made relating to the above mentioned fields by using what are called Molecular descriptors.

There are mainly three types of descriptors:

1. Degree based molecular descriptors
2. Distance based molecular descriptors
3. Eigenvalue based molecular descriptors

A pair of molecular descriptors known as the first Zagreb index $M_1(G)$ and the second Zagreb index $M_2(G)$, are the first degree-based topological indices and the first appeared in the topological formula for the total π -electron energy of conjugated molecules that has been derived by Gutman and Trinajstić [6], the first and second Zagreb indices are defined as:

$$M_1(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (d_u + d_v) \quad M_2(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (d_u \cdot d_v)$$

Suleyman Ediz [11] defined the first reduced Zagreb index and studied the characterization of minimum and maximum graphs. Boris Furtula et al [4] and Mukhtar Ahmad et. al [8] studied the second and third reduced Zagreb indices.

Vukicevic and Gasperov [14] proposed 148 discrete adriatic indices and evaluated their predictive properties. Among them, just 20 indices were selected as significant predictors of physical-chemical properties. The symmetric division degree index, which was selected in as a significant predictor of total surface area of polychlorobiphenyls and for which the extremal graphs obtained with the help of MathChem have a particularly simple and elegant structure.

A variation of Randic connectivity index is the sum-connectivity index, it was presented by Zhou and Trinajstic [5]. They determined upper and lower bounds of this index for trees in terms of other graph invariants.

Ivan Gutman [7] conceived the IRF irregularity index of the graph and Reti et. al [10] studied IRDIF, IRLF, IRLA and IRB irregularity indices. For more information on molecular descriptors refer [3–5, 7–10, 12]

Amino Acids are the organic compounds that combine to form peptide and proteins, hence they are referred to as the building blocks for peptide and proteins. Amino acids are organic compounds containing the basic amino groups ($-NH_2$) and carboxyl groups ($-COOH$). Altogether, there are twenty amino acids, which are involved in the construction of proteins.

Altogether, there are twenty amino acids, which are involved in the construction of proteins. The chemical structure of the AAs was drawn by Gauss View Software and then was transferred into Gaussian03 program to optimize the physicochemical properties of the molecules at the RHF/6-31 G level of theory. The heat capacity (C_v), entropy (S) and thermal energy (E_{th}) of twenty essential (AAs) is taken from the quantum mechanics methodology.

The following molecular descriptors are considered for the study.

Topological index	Abbreviations	Definition
Symmetric division degree index [14]	SDDI	$\sum_{uv \in E(G)} \left(\frac{d_u}{d_v} + \frac{d_v}{d_u} \right)$
Sum-connectivity index [5]	SCI	$\sum_{uv \in E(G)} \frac{1}{\sqrt{d_u + d_v}}$
First Reduced Zagreb index [11]	MR_1I	$\sum_{uv \in E(G)} (d_u - 1) + (d_v - 1) $
Second Reduced Zagreb Index [4]	MR_2I	$\sum_{uv \in E(G)} [(d_u - 1) \cdot (d_v - 1)]$
Third Reduced Zagreb index [8]	MR_3I	$\sum_{uv \in E(G)} (d_u - 1) - (d_v - 1) $
Irregularity index [7]	IRFI	$\sum_{uv \in E(G)} (d_u - d_v)^2$
Irregularity index [10]	IRDIFI	$\sum_{uv \in E(G)} \left \frac{d_u}{d_v} - \frac{d_v}{d_u} \right $
Irregularity index [10]	IRLFI	$\sum_{uv \in E(G)} \frac{ d_u - d_v }{\sqrt{d_u \cdot d_v}}$
Irregularity index [10]	IRLAI	$2 \cdot \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \frac{ d_u - d_v }{d_u + d_v}$
Irregularity index [10]	IRBI	$\sum_{uv \in E(G)} (\sqrt{d_u} - \sqrt{d_v})^2$

Table 1. The molecular structure [2] and molecular graphs of Amino acids

Amino acids	Molecular structure	Molecular Graphs
Alanine		
Valine		
Leucine		
Isoleucine		
Phenylalanine		
Tryptophan		
Methionine		
Lysine		
Arginine		
Histidine		

Amino acids	Molecular structure	Molecular Graph
Glycine		
Serine		
Threonine		
Cysteine		
Tyrosine		
Asparagine		
Glutamine		
Aspartic Acid		
Glutamic Acid		

2 Data Set of Amino acids

Table 2: Physicochemical properties of Amino acids [1]

S.No	Amino acid	Abbreviations	<i>S</i>	<i>Cv</i>	<i>E_{th}</i>
1.	Alanine	A	335.929	97.657	320.347
2.	Valine	V	389.576	137.643	486.677
3.	Leucine	L	403.027	141.447	567.268
4.	Isoleucine	I	415.053	155.851	570.842
5.	Phenylalanine	F	439.163	163.759	564.124
6.	Tryptophan	W	469.355	195.908	653.915
7.	Methionine	M	441.638	157.783	495.184
8.	Lysine	K	456.556	173.871	623.819
9.	Arginine	R	504.868	198.993	617.992
10.	Histidine	H	429.624	148.54	480.917
11.	Glycine	G	309.169	76.356	237.779
12.	Serine	S	351.032	108.282	338.889
13.	Threonine	T	388.372	135.515	418.309
14.	Cysteine	C	370.331	117.332	323.607
15.	Tyrosine	Y	458.989	181.909	578.499
16.	Asparagine	N	389.901	136.38	408.779
17.	Glutamine	Q	433.294	151.179	494.042
18.	Aspartic Acid	D	383.088	127.92	382.800
19.	Glutamic Acid	E	473.731	168.88	457.129

Table 3: Molecular descriptors of Amino acids.

S.No	Amino acid	Abbreviations	SDDI	SCI	MR_1I	MR_2I	MR_3I	IRFI	IRDIFI	IRLFI	IRLAI	IRBI
1.	Alanine	A	15.333	2.408	12	4	8	16	10.666	4.618	4.0	2.143
2.	Valine	V	20.666	3.316	18	8	10	20	13.333	5.773	5.0	2.679
3.	Leucine	L	23.0	3.802	20	8	12	22	14.999	6.589	5.8	2.881
4.	Isoleucine	I	19.0	3.418	16	6	10	16	11.999	5.395	4.866	2.082
5.	Phenylalanine	F	28.666	5.697	30	16	10	16	11.3333	5.097	4.6	2.011
6.	Tryptophan	W	37.000	7.408	44	28	12	18	12.999	5.913	5.4	2.213
7.	Methionine	M	20.666	3.932	18	8	8	14	10.333	4.579	4.066	1.880
8.	Lysine	K	22.666	4.432	20	9	8	14	10.333	4.579	4.066	1.880
9.	Arginine	R	28.999	5.302	26	11	12	22	14.999	6.589	5.8	2.881
10.	Histidine	H	26.666	5.197	28	15	10	16	11.333	5.097	4.6	2.011
11.	Glycine	G	11.333	2.024	8	2	6	10	7.666	3.424	3.066	1.344
12.	Serine	S	16.666	2.932	14	6	8	14	10.333	4.579	4.066	1.880
13.	Threonine	T	20.666	3.316	18	8	10	20	13.333	5.773	5.0	2.679
14.	Cysteine	C	16.666	2.932	14	6	8	14	10.333	4.579	4.066	1.880
15.	Tyrosine	Y	32.333	6.091	34	18	14	22	15.666	7.068	6.399	2.749
16.	Asparagine	N	23.0	3.802	20	8	12	22	14.999	6.589	5.8	2.881
17.	Glutamine	Q	24.999	4.302	22	9	12	22	14.999	6.589	5.8	2.881
18.	Aspartic	D	23.0	3.802	20	8	12	22	14.999	6.589	5.8	2.881
19.	Glutamic	E	24.999	4.302	22	9	12	22	14.9999	6.589	5.8	2.881

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Intercorrelation analysis between molecular descriptors:

The intercorrelation between 10 molecular descriptors(SDDI, SCI, MR_1I , MR_2I , MR_3I , IRFI, IRDIFI, IRLFI, IRLAI and IRBI) is carried out in table 4 and the values for pair of indices is judged by correlation coefficient r . For $r > 0.97$ it is highly intercorrelated, for $r > 0.9$ it is appreciably intercorrelated, for $r < 0.9$ it is weakly intercorrelated and for $r < 0.5$ it is not intercorrelated [13].

Table 4: Intercorrelation of molecular descriptors.

	SDDI	SCI	MR_1I	MR_2I	MR_3I	IRFI	IRDIFI	IRLFI	IRLAI	IRBI
SDDI	1	0.974	0.972	0.905	0.751	0.542	0.584	0.624	0.664	0.457
SCI		1	0.984	0.949	0.597	0.340	0.392	0.441	0.491	0.246
MR_1I			1	0.978	0.621	0.372	0.415	0.461	0.510	0.275
MR_2I				1	0.473	0.207	0.249	0.298	0.351	0.108
MR_3I					1	0.929	0.959	0.975	0.987	0.884
IRFI						1	0.990	0.980	0.964	0.993
IRDIFI							1	0.998	0.989	0.977
IRLFI								1	0.997	0.960
IRLAI									1	0.936
IRBI										1

From intercorrelation analysis, it concludes that most of the pairs are highly intercorrelated, with the pair $IRDIFI$ and $IRLFI$ the most i.e. $r = 0.998$ and the pair MR_2I and $IRBI$ are not intercorrelated with $r = 0.108$.

- SDDI is highly intercorelated with SCI, MR_1I , appreciably intercorelated with MR_2I , weakly intercorelated with MR_3I , IIRFI, IRDIFI, IRLFI, IRLAI, IRBI and not intercorelated with IRBI indices.
- SCI is highly intercorelated with SDDI, MR_1I , appreciably intercorelated with MR_2I , weakly intercorelated with MR_3I , and not intercorelated with IRFI, IRDIFI, IRLFI, IRLAI, IRBI indices.
- MR_1I is highly intercorelated with SDDI, SCI, MR_2I , weakly intercorelated with MR_3I , IRLAI and not intercorelated with IRFI, IRDIFI, IRLFI, IRBI indices.
- MR_2I is highly intercorelated with MR_1I , appreciably intercorelated with SDDI, SCI, and not intercorelated with MR_3I , IRFI, IRDIFI, IRLFI, IRLAI, IRBI indices.
- MR_3I is highly intercorelated with IRLFI, IRLAI, appreciably intercorelated with IRFI, IRDIFI, weakly intercorelated with SDDI, SCI, MR_1I , IRBI and not intercorelated with MR_2I indices.
- IRFI is highly intercorelated with IRDIFI, IRLFI, IRBI, appreciably intercorelated with MR_3I , IRLAI, weakly intercorelated with SDDI and not intercorelated with SCI, MR_1I , MR_2I indices.
- IRDIFI is highly intercorelated with IRFI, IRLFI, IRLAI, IRBI, appreciably intercorelated with MR_3I , weakly intercorelated with SDDI and not intercorelated with SCI, MR_1I , MR_2I indices.
- IRLFI is highly intercorelated with MR_3I , IRFI, IRDIFI, IRLAI, IRBI, weakly intercorelated with SDDI and not intercorelated with SCI, MR_1I , MR_2I indices.
- IRLAI is highly intercorelated with MR_3I , IRDIFI, IRLFI, appreciably intercorelated with IRFI, IRBI, weakly intercorelated with SDDI, MR_1I and not intercorelated with SCI, MR_2I indices.
- IRBI is highly intercorelated with IRFI, IRDIFI, appreciably intercorelated with IRLFI, IRLAI, weakly intercorelated with MR_3I and not intercorelated with

SDDI, SCI, MR_1I , MR_2I indices.

3.2 Regression Models

Regression models are statistical tools used to describe the relationship between a dependent variable and one or more independent variables. In this study the independent variables are the molecular descriptors and dependent variable is physicochemical properties of amino acids. In the following models n , F , SF and Sig represents the population, F-values, standard error of the estimate and statistically significant respectively.

Linear Regression assumes a straight-line relationship between variables, expressed as

$$PP = a(MD) + b$$

where a is the intercept and b is the slope. It is suitable when the relationship between the variables is proportional.

Table 5: The correlation coefficient r for linear regression model between molecular descriptors and physicochemical properties.

	SDDI	SCI	MR_1I	MR_2I	MR_3I	IRFI	IRDIFI	IRLFI	IRLAI	IRBI
S	0.922	0.915	0.736	0.641	0.600	0.443	0.503	0.535	0.567	0.387
Cv	0.970	0.963	0.901	0.722	0.635	0.453	0.521	0.558	0.595	0.390
E_{th}	0.753	0.766	0.703	0.640	0.515	0.389	0.443	0.468	0.494	0.351

The linear regression models are as follows:

$$S = (6.804)(\pm 1.142)(SDDI) + 256.529(\pm 27.109)$$

$$n = 19 \quad F = 35.475 \quad SF = 29.793 \quad Sig = 0.000$$

$$Cv = (4.542)(\pm 0.623)(SDDI) + 41.766(\pm 14795)$$

$$n = 19 \quad F = 53.068 \quad SF = 16.260 \quad Sig = 0.000$$

$$S = (31.012)(\pm 5.346)(SCI) + 284.782(\pm 23.135)$$

$$n = 19 \quad F = 33.649 \quad SF = 30.325 \quad Sig = 0.000$$

$$Cv = (20698)(\pm 2.944)(SCI) + 60.641(\pm 12742)$$

$$n = 19 \quad F = 49.415 \quad SF = 16.701 \quad Sig = 0.000$$

$$Cv = (3.074)(\pm 0.557)(MR_1I) + 80.694(\pm 12.686)$$

$$n = 19 \quad F = 30.440 \quad SF = 19.761 \quad Sig = 0.000$$

The linear regression models are depicted in the following figures.

Figure 1. Linear regression model of S and Cv with $SDDI$

Figure 2. Linear regression model of S and Cv with SCI

Figure 3. Linear regression model of Cv with MR_1I

Logarithmic Regression models relationships where the rate of change decreases over time, often expressed as

$$PP = a \ln(MD) + b$$

and is useful for scenarios like diminishing returns.

Table 6: The correlation coefficient r for logarithmic regression model between molecular descriptors and physicochemical properties.

	SDDI	SCI	MR_1I	MR_2I	MR_3I	IRFI	IRDIFI	IRLFI	IRLAI	IRBI
S	0.955	0.975	0.918	0.782	0.617	0.472	0.527	0.557	0.587	0.420
Cv	0.993	0.908	0.966	0.938	0.654	0.490	0.550	0.585	0.619	0.430
E_{th}	0.777	0.904	0.756	0.727	0.544	0.425	0.474	0.498	0.523	0.388

The logarithmic regression models are as follows:

$$S = (155.971)(\pm 22.994) \ln(SDDI) + (-70.513)(\pm 71.521)$$

$$n = 19 \quad F = 46.011 \quad SF = 27.188 \quad Sig = 0.000$$

$$Cv = (102.753)(\pm 12.585) \ln(SDDI) + (-172.323)(\pm 39.144)$$

$$n = 19 \quad F = 66.664 \quad SF = 14.880 \quad Sig = 0.000$$

$$S = (138.291)(\pm 18.599) \ln(SCI) + (233.460)(\pm 26.119)$$

$$n = 19 \quad F = 55.285 \quad SF = 25.384 \quad Sig = 0.000$$

$$Cv = (90.554)(\pm 10.132) \ln(SCI) + (22.099)(\pm 14.229)$$

$$n = 19 \quad F = 79.873 \quad SF = 13.829 \quad Sig = 0.000$$

$$Eth = (311.615)(\pm 57.592) \ln(SCI) + (49.217)(\pm 78.520)$$

$$n = 19 \quad F = 29.276 \quad SF = 69.084 \quad Sig = 0.000$$

$$S = (138.291)(\pm 18.599) \ln(MR_1I) + (233.460)(\pm 26.119)$$

$$n = 19 \quad F = 55285 \quad SF = 25.384 \quad Sig = 0.000$$

$$Cv = (90.554)(\pm 10.132) \ln(MR_1I) + (22.099)(\pm 14.229)$$

$$n = 19 \quad F = 79.873 \quad SF = 13.829 \quad Sig = 0.000$$

$$Cv = (47.208)(\pm 7.469) \ln(MR_2I) + (45.127)(\pm 16.498)$$

$$n = 19 \quad F = 39.944 \quad SF = 18.037 \quad Sig = 0.000$$

The logarithmic regression models are depicted in the following figures.

Figure 4. Logarithmic regression model of S and Cv with $SDDI$

Figure 5. Logarithmic regression model of S and Cv with SCI

Figure 6. Logarithmic regression model of E_{th} with and SCI and S with MR_{1I}

Figure 7. Logarithmic regression model of Cv with MR_{1I} and MR_{2I}

Quadratic Regression extends linear regression to include a squared term,

$$PP = a(MD)^2 + b(MD) + c$$

capturing parabolic relationships where the dependent variable changes direction at some point.

Table 7: The correlation coefficient r for quadratic regression model between molecular descriptors and physicochemical properties.

	SDDI	SCI	MR_1I	MR_2I	MR_3I	IRFI	IRDIFI	IRLFI	IRLAI	IRBI
S	0.965	0.904	0.944	0.791	0.621	0.510	0.557	0.580	0.604	0.486
Cv	0.992	0.913	0.966	0.919	0.658	0.560	0.603	0.622	0.644	0.543
E_{th}	0.780	0.919	0.769	0.747	0.568	0.505	0.542	0.555	0.569	0.496

The quadratic regression model is given by

$$S = (-0.267)(\pm 0.125)(SDDI)^2 + (19.640)(\pm 6.102)(SDDI) + (112.196)(\pm 71.963)$$

$$n = 19 \quad F = 23.728 \quad SF = 27.092 \quad Sig = 0.000$$

$$Cv = (-0.122)(\pm 0.071)(SDDI)^2 + (10.393)(\pm 3.471)(SDDI) + (-24.026)(\pm 40.932)$$

$$n = 19 \quad F = 31.005 \quad SF = 15.410 \quad Sig = 0.000$$

$$S = (-8.888)(\pm 2.420)(SCI)^2 + (112.747)(\pm 22.621)(SCI) + (113.887)(\pm 49.735)$$

$$n = 19 \quad F = 35.930 \quad SF = 23.024 \quad Sig = 0.000$$

$$Cv = (-4.271)(\pm 1.461)(SCI)^2 + (59.972)(\pm 13.655)(SCI) + (-21.475)(\pm 30.022)$$

$$n = 19 \quad F = 39.951 \quad SF = 13.898 \quad Sig = 0.000$$

$$E_{th} = (-23.746)(\pm 12.142)(SCI)^2 + (272.797)(\pm 100.722)(SCI) + (-214.317)(\pm 199.317)$$

$$n = 19 \quad F = 15.269 \quad SF = 68.885 \quad Sig = 0.000$$

$$S = (-0.215)(\pm 0.070)(MR_1I)^2 + (15.461)(\pm 3.660)(MR_1I) + (195.496)(\pm 43.796)$$

$$n = 19 \quad F = 19.768 \quad SF = 28.960 \quad Sig = 0.000$$

$$Cv = (-0.108)(\pm 0.041)(MR_1I)^2 + (8.581)(\pm 2.152)(MR_1I) + (19.486)(\pm 25.754)$$

$$n = 19 \quad F = 23.939 \quad SF = 17.030 \quad Sig = 0.000$$

$$Cv = (-0.255)(\pm 0.095)(MR_2I)^2 + (11.408)(\pm 2.884)(MR_2I) + (66.886)(\pm 17.472)$$

$$n = 19 \quad F = 16.258 \quad SF = 19.541 \quad Sig = 0.000$$

The quadratic regression models are depicted in the following figures.

Figure 8. Quadratic regression model of S and Cv with $SDDI$

Figure 9. Quadratic regression model of S and Cv with SCI

Figure 10. Quadratic regression model of E_{th} with and SCI and S with MR_1I

Figure 11. Quadratic regression model of Cv with MR_1I and MR_2I

Cubic Regression incorporates a cubic term,

$$PP = a(MD)^3 + b(MD)^2 + c(MD) + d$$

enabling it to model more complex relationships with multiple inflection points.

Table 8: The correlation coefficient r for cubic regression model between molecular descriptors and physicochemical properties.

	SDDI	SCI	MR_1I	MR_2I	MR_3I	IRFI	IRDIFI	IRLFI	IRLAI	IRBI
S	0.966	0.905	0.948	0.928	0.621	0.510	0.557	0.580	0.604	0.486
Cv	0.993	0.920	0.978	0.961	0.658	0.560	0.603	0.622	0.644	0.543
E_{th}	0.783	0.920	0.772	0.748	0.568	0.505	0.542	0.555	0.569	0.496

The cubic regression models are as follows:

$$S = (-0.007)(\pm 0.018)(SDDI)^3 + (0.259)(\pm 1.300)(SDDI)^2 + (7.726)(\pm 29.977)(SDDI) + (196.144)(\pm 219.381)$$

$$n = 19 \quad F = 15.048 \quad SF = 27.828 \quad Sig = 0.000$$

$$Cv = (0.005)(\pm 0.010)(SDDI)^3 + (-0.488)(\pm 0.737)(SDDI)^2 + (18.693)(\pm 17.004)(SDDI) + (-82.511)(\pm 124.438)$$

$$n = 19 \quad F = 19.783 \quad SF = 15.785 \quad Sig = 0.000$$

$$S = (0.416)(\pm 1.588)(SCI)^3 + (-14.711)(\pm 22.360)(SCI)^2 \\ + (137.934)(\pm 98.884)(SCI) + (80.346)(\pm 137.856)$$

$$n = 19 \quad F = 22.582 \quad SF = 23.725 \quad Sig = 0.000$$

$$Cv = (1.055)(\pm 0.921)(SCI)^3 + (-19.030)(\pm 12.973)(SCI)^2 \\ + (123.802)(\pm 57.373)(SCI) + (-106.480)(\pm 79.985)$$

$$n = 19 \quad F = 27.588 \quad SF = 13.765 \quad Sig = 0.000$$

$$E_{th} = (3.172)(\pm 11.941)(SCI)^3 + (-61.976)(\pm 144.463)(SCI)^2 \\ + (417.669)(\pm 555.205)(SCI) + (-385.957)(\pm 678.226)$$

$$n = 19 \quad F = 9.572 \quad SF = 71.123 \quad Sig = 0.000$$

$$S = (0.004)(\pm 0.007)(MR_1I)^3 + (-0.538)(\pm 0.551)(MR_1I)^2 \\ + (22.834)(\pm 13.014)(MR_1I) + (145.836)(\pm 95.129)$$

$$n = 19 \quad F = 12.760 \quad SF = 29.567 \quad Sig = 0.000$$

$$Cv = (0.005)(\pm 0.004)(MR_1I)^3 + (-0.474)(\pm 0.314)(MR_1I)^2 \\ + (16.936)(\pm 7.407)(MR_1I) + (-36.790)(\pm 54.141)$$

$$n = 19 \quad F = 16.807 \quad SF = 16.828 \quad Sig = 0.000$$

$$S = (0.036)(\pm 0.022)(MR_2I)^3 + (-2.093)(\pm 0.967)(MR_2I)^2 \\ + (38.879)(\pm 12.257)(MR_2I) + (220.026)(\pm 45.870)$$

$$n = 19 \quad F = 10.899 \quad SF = 31.249 \quad Sig = 0.000$$

$$Cv = (0.025)(\pm 0.012)(MR_2I)^3 + (-1.365)(\pm 0.553)(MR_2I)^2 \\ + (24.611)(\pm 7.009)(MR_2I) + (24.596)(\pm 26.230)$$

$$n = 19 \quad F = 14.339 \quad SF = 17.869 \quad Sig = 0.000$$

The cubic regression models are depicted in the following figures.

Figure 12. Cubic regression model of S and Cv with $SDDI$

Figure 13. Cubic regression model of S and Cv with SCI

Figure 14. Cubic regression model of E_{th} with and SCI and S with MR_{1I}

Figure 15. Cubic regression model of Cv with MR_1I and S with MR_2I

Figure 16. Cubic regression model of Cv with MR_2I

3.3 Analysis

The following analysis can be made from linear, logarithmic, quadratic and cubic models:

- In linear regression model, $SDDI$ is showing good correlation with S and Cv with maximum $r = 0.970$ for Cv , SCI is showing good correlation with S , and Cv with maximum $r = 0.963$ for S , MR_1I is showing good correlation with Cv with maximum $r = 0.901$ for Cv , rest of the molecular descriptors are not correlated well with physicochemical properties.
- In logarithmic regression model, $SDDI$ is showing good correlation with S and Cv with maximum $r = 0.993$ for Cv , SCI is showing good correlation with S , Cv and E_{th} with maximum $r = 0.975$ for S , MR_1I is showing good correlation with S and

C_v with maximum $r = 0.966$ for C_v , MR_2I is showing good correlation with S and C_v with maximum $r = 0.938$ for C_v , rest of the molecular descriptors are not correlated well with physicochemical properties.

- In quadratic regression model, $SDDI$ is showing good correlation with S and C_v with maximum $r = 0.992$ for C_v , SCI is showing good correlation with S , C_v and E_{th} with maximum $r = 0.919$ for E_{th} , MR_1I is showing good correlation with S and C_v with maximum $r = 0.966$ for C_v , MR_2I is showing good correlation with C_v with maximum $r = 0.919$ for C_v , rest of the molecular descriptors are not correlated well with physicochemical properties.
- In cubic regression model, $SDDI$ is showing good correlation with S and C_v with maximum $r = 0.993$ for C_v , SCI is showing good correlation with S , C_v and E_{th} with maximum $r = 0.920$ for C_v and E_{th} , MR_1I is showing good correlation with S and C_v with maximum $r = 0.978$ for C_v , MR_2I is showing good correlation with S and C_v with maximum $r = 0.961$ for C_v , rest of the molecular descriptors are not correlated well with physicochemical properties.
- Higher-order regression models (quadratic and cubic) are generally more suitable for capturing relationships between molecular descriptors and physicochemical properties. $SDDI$ and SCI are key descriptors for predicting S and C_v . Cubic regression yields the best results $SDDI$, SCI and MR_1I .

4 Conclusion

In this study, a quantitative structure-property relationship (QSPR) analysis is conducted to investigate the correlation between a set of 10 degree-based molecular descriptors and key physicochemical properties like heat capacity (C_v), entropy (S), and thermal energy (E_{th}) of 19 naturally occurring amino acids. Multiple regression models, including linear, logarithmic, quadratic, and cubic are employed to evaluate the predictive capabilities of the selected descriptors. The findings demonstrate that the degree-based molecular descriptors exhibit strong predictive potential for the studied physicochemical properties.

Molecular descriptors like $SDDI$, SCI and MR_1I are able to predict the physicochemical properties of Amino acids.

References

- [1] Afsaneh Safari, Fatemah. Shafiei, QSPR Models of Physicochemical Properties of Natural Amino Acids by Using Topological Indices and MLR Method, *J.Chem.Soc.Pak.*, 39(05) 2017 752-757.
- [2] Bello Abdullahi Umar, Adamu Uzairu, Gideon Adamu Shallangwa, Quantum Modeling and Molecular Dynamic Simulation of some Amino Acids and Related Compounds on their Corrosion Inhibition of Steel in Acidic Media, *Portugaliae Electrochimica Acta.*, 38(5) (2020) 313-329.
- [3] A.R. Bindusree, N. Cangul I., V. Lokesha, S. Cevik A., Zagreb polynomials of three graph operators, *Filomat.* 30 (2016) 1979-1986.
- [4] Boris Furtula, Ivan Gutmana, Süleyman Ediz, On difference of Zagreb indices, *Discrete Applied Mathematics* 178 (2014) 83-88.
- [5] Bo Zhou and Trinajsti, On a novel connectivity index, *Journal of Mathematical Chemistry* 46 (2009) 1252-1270.
- [6] I. Gutman, N. Trinajstic, Graph Theory and Molecular Orbitals, Total π -electron energy of alternate hydrocarbons, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 17 (1972) 535-538.
- [7] Ivan Gutman, Topological Indices And Irregularity Measures, *Bulletien of the International Mathematical Virtual Institue*, 8 (2018), 469-475.
- [8] Mukhtar Ahmad et. al, On Degree-Based Topological Indices of Petersen Subdivision Graph, *Eur. J. Math. Anal.*, 3(20) (2023).
- [9] Rachanna Kanabura, S.K.Giregola, Akshata Nagaral, Priyanka Badave, Rekha Sannakkai, Renuka Sasalattia, QSPR Analysis of Chemical Graph Theory, *Gen.Lett. Math.*, 9(1) (2020) 9-16.

- [10] T. Reti, R. Sharafdini, A. Dregelyi-Kiss, and H. Haghbin, Graph irregularity indices used as molecular descriptors in QSPR studies, *MATCH Communications in Mathematical and in Computer Chemistry*, 79 (2018) 509-524.
- [11] Suleyman Ediz, On the reduced first Zagreb index of graphs, *Pacific Journal of Applied Mathematics*, 8(2) (2016) 99-102.
- [12] Tanweer Ul Islam, Zeeshan Saleem Mufti, Aqsa Ameen, Muhammad Nauman Aslam and Ali Tabraiz, On Certain Aspects of Topological Indices, *Hindawi Journal of Mathematics*, 2021, (2021).
- [13] N. Trinajstić, S. Nikoli, S. C. Basak, I. Lukovits, Distance Indices and Their Hyper-Counterparts: Intercorrelation and Use in the Structure-Property Modeling, *SAR and QSAR in Environmental Research*, (2001) 31-54.
- [14] D. Vukicevic, M. Gasperov, Bond additive modeling 1. Adriatic indices, *Croat. Chem. Acta.*, 83 (2010) 243-260.